

 Infinitech

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Bridging the Digital Finance Skills Gap

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AltCoins	Alternative Coins
AML	Anti-Money Laundering
BTC	BitCoin
CDP	Career Development Paths
CGMA	Chartered Global Management Accountant
DL	Deep Learnings
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technologies
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
ETH	Ethereum
FinTech	Financial Technology
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GenZ	Generation Z
HR	Human Resources
ICAEW	Institute of Chartered Accountants in England and Wales
KYC	Know Your Customer
MiFID	Markets in Financial Instruments Directive
ML	Machine Learnings
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PFM	Personal Finance Management
PSD	Payment Services Directive
UCITS	Undertakings for Collective Investment in Transferable Securities
WEF	World Economic Forum

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1. Introduction

Compared to other industries, the finance sector has been quite resistant to technological changes across the years. However, recent changes in the market are now reshaping the finance sector’s approach towards digital transformation [1]. Several players in the banking and finance market including traditional competitors, FinTechs, new bank entrants, facilitators and customers are contributing to this shift. For example, traditional competitors are resharing their business models, customers demand integrated and tailored customer service, new market entrants can better serve the needs of tech-savvy younger generations (e.g., genZ, younger millennials), substitute products are offered by financial-technology (FinTech) companies and large consumer ecosystems (e.g., Apple, Google) which take new intermediary roles in facilitating transactions (e.g., based on Payment Services like Apple Pay) (Figure 1). Digital technologies are imposing changes in the business models of financial organizations, while intensifying competition in customer acquisition and providing opportunities for deploying novel product and service offerings.

Figure 1 - Key players shifting the banking and finance sector towards digital transformation

For more than five years, financial organizations are accelerating their digital transformation in order to take advantage of technology-based opportunities and to sustain the relevant competition. Investments in digital finance and skyrocketing as finance leaders (e.g., JPMorgan¹) invest billions of dollars in the development and deployment of digital technologies like Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI). In this context, financial leaders underline the importance of investments in complementary assets like training and skills, which could help financial organizations to successfully deploy and fully leverage digital finance technologies². The lack of digital skills is a serious set-back against

¹ <https://www.jpmorganchase.com/news-stories/tech-investment-could-disrupt-banking>

² <https://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/fill-finances-skill-gaps>

realizing the full potential of digital technologies in the banking and finance sector. For instance, it has been estimated that the lack of data literacy can cost an enterprise up to 1% of its revenue. In 2021, 80% of finance organizations increased their use of data analytics tools in 2021, which is indicative of the importance of data analytics skills.

The process of filling the digital finance skills gaps is an essential part of the digital transformation of financial organizations, which are under pressure not only to modernize their technology infrastructure, but also to realize a wider cultural and management shift towards digital finance. The upskilling and reskilling of finance sector employees is a key enabler of this shift. In 2018, the World Economic Forum (WEF) global survey of companies, banking and finance is one of the top industries where reskilling of employees is particularly important [2]. Also, the survey acknowledges that all occupations of sector from scientific to professional, middle-level and vocational will need to develop new digital skills.

To design and implement effective reskilling and upskilling processes, financial organizations need to understand the wide spectrum of digital finance skills, as well as their role in specific technologies and applications. To this end, they can greatly benefit from structured representations of different digital skills, including their interrelationships with other skills and digital finance applications. Such structured representations of digital finance skills can be conveniently characterized as Digital Finance Skills Frameworks (DFSFs). In recent years, various DFSFs have been proposed by consulting firms, research organizations and policy makers. Nevertheless, there is generally a lack of DFSFs that address skills associated with the emerging wave of Big Data and AI applications in digital finance, which is the area of focus of the EU funded project INFINITECH.

Motivated by the gap in DFSFs this whitepaper introduces and empirically validates a Digital Finance Skills Framework (DFSF) for the banking and finance sector. It first presents desk research on various skills frameworks for the target sector. Accordingly, it introduces a DFSF that addresses different knowledge areas and competences. The framework emphasizes digital skills that are relevant to INFINITECH, notably skills linked to Big Data, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and blockchain applications. It aims at complementing the INFINITECH technologies with the complementary resources that foster the development of the ever-important human capital. The presented framework is a very useful tool for digital finance professionals, human resources professionals and policy makers that deal with the specifications of skills development programs and policies.

The introduced framework has driven the development of a digital finance skills survey, which was completed by over sixty (60) professionals of the finance and banking sector, including professionals working in different departments of financial institution. The goal of the survey was to solicit the professional's opinion on the relevant importance of the different competence and skills that comprise the digital finance framework. Key findings from the survey are accordingly analyzed and discussed. The discussion gives rise to recommendations about skills profiles that can be based on the introduced framework.

2. Digital Skills Frameworks in Banking and Finance

Various digital finance skills frameworks have been proposed from a variety of different organizations, including education policy makers, skills development organizations, research organizations and consulting firms. Most of them identify finance and digital skills, while outlining their interrelationships. Some of the most prominent examples follow:

- **The Chartered Global Management Accountant (CGMA®) designation** has released a competency framework [3] covering key knowledge areas which are considered essential for the finance professional. These encapsulate five clusters of knowledge areas including technical skills, business skills, people skills, leadership skills and digital skills. It also provides a detailed definition of each one of these five types of skills. Moreover, it highlights that skill categories requirements vary across the different career levels of the finance professional. However, digital skills are the category which is expected to be key for finance professionals across different career levels. The study further elaborates on digital skills such that they are dismantled in terms of information and digital literacy, digital content creation, problem-solving, data strategy and planning, data analytics and data visualization.
- **A national-level study in the Czech Republic outlines and justifies the need for developing the financial sector employees' digital skills [4]**, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors draw on empirical data from the banking and insurance sectors in the Czech Republic to shed light on the required digital competences. In the presented study 60% of respondents highlighted problem solving in the digital environment skills, and basic skills in data entry and processing. Likewise, 50% of the respondent identified advanced analytical and mathematical skills, and database management skills as important. Other skills identified by a smaller part of the sample population included software development skills, digital project management skills, web page development skills and digital strategy and leadership skills.
- **The study in [5] introduces a digital financial competence framework for the financial sector.** The framework consists of six thematic areas each of which specifies relevant. Main thematic areas include information and communication, the financial landscape, service uptake, managing finances, safety and risk management and problem-solving. The information and communication thematic area is closer related to digital finance skills. This thematic area encapsulates three competences, namely: (i) Browsing, searching, and filtering information; (ii) Evaluating information; and (iii) Interacting through technologies. Other relevant thematic areas include skills such as the understanding of digital environment and digital financial services consumer protection regulations, as well as the rights and responsibilities of digital financial services consumers. It also outlines additional digital elements for services uptake, such as making digital payments, managing digital financial records, and managing digital financial services. Moreover, the safety and risk management thematic area includes additional competencies such risk management associated with the use of digital platforms and digital financial products. Finally, the importance of problem solving is also highlighted and linked to competences relevant to solving technical problems and responding to needs through digital technologies.
- **The Institute of Chartered Accountants in England and Wales (ICAEW) has released a list of data science skills recommended to finance professionals [6].** These include data strategy, ethics, data intuition, data analysis and interpretation, communication and data visualization, programming and tools, statistics, maths modelling and algorithms. The framework includes detailed information about each one of these skills categories. For instance, the data strategy cluster of skills includes the

ability to conduct data governance and lead data collection investments and data science programmes as well as holding an overall knowledge of the digital landscape towards choose the technological investments which contribute to the strategy of the organization. As another example, ethics refer to expending the accounting profession code of conduct to encapsulate privacy, data security, transparency, decision-making bias in algorithms. Likewise, data intuition is relevant to the ability to draw on data to solving business problems, including framing a problem such that it can be answered with data.

- **A McKinsey & Co report on the next generation of technology transformation in financial services [7] identifies traits of CIOs (Chief Information Officers) in financial services.** First, CIOs need to be business leaders in order to understand the technology and how it could assist the business' strategy. Second, they need to serve as change agents. This skill encapsulates being part of the business boards, networking on boards beyond the business in order to gain deep business and industry knowledge. Along the same lines as a change agent, they need to embrace the adoption of new technologies into the business' everyday strategy while continuously reimagining the role of technology, reinventing technology delivery, and future-proofing the foundation. Third, they also need to be talent scouts. Attracting new technology talent and being able to develop diverse career paths for them in the organization is important. Fourth, CIOs need to hold culture revolutionary skills such that they can better support their effective talent strategy and build an engineering community model which encapsulates collaboration across different technology teams and other business department. Fifth, they also need to be tech translators, such that they can further educate the business leaders about new technologies, their implications, and potential applications for the business.
- **The European Commission's Digital Competencies (DigComp) framework [8] has identified different thematic areas of skills enhancement capturing 21 competences.** These areas include: Information & data literacy; Communication & collaboration; Digital content creation; Safety; Problem solving. The framework identifies different proficiency levels including Foundational, Intermediate, Advanced and Highly Specialized. The competences included in the framework under each thematic area are as follows. Under the Information & data literacy, competences included are browsing, searching and filtering data, information and digital content, evaluating data, information and digital content, managing data, information and digital content. The Communication & collaboration area includes competencies such as interacting through digital technologies, sharing through digital technologies, engaging in citizenship through digital technologies, collaborating through digital technologies, netiquette and managing digital identity. Digital content creation includes competences on developing digital content, integrating and re-elaborating digital content, copyright and licenses and programming. Safety encapsulates competences such as protecting devices, protecting personal data and privacy, protecting health and well-being, protecting the environment. Finally, problem solving is about developing competences on solving technical problems, identifying needs and technological responses, creatively using digital technologies, and identifying digital competence gaps.

The extant literature lacks a framework that focuses explicitly on the digital finance skills and competences for the banking and finance professionals. Indeed, most of the existing literature which addresses skills enhancement for the banking and finance professionals, focuses on providing an overview of all skills required for the professionals, of which digital skills is a small subset. For instance, most of the frameworks identified throughout our literature review cover a wider spectrum of skills in which digital skills are partly included

under other competences identified. An in-depth analysis of the digital finance skills is beyond the scope of the existing skills frameworks dedicated to the needs of the banking and finance professionals. Along the same lines, very few publications draw on empirical data to formulate or validate their frameworks. To address these gaps, we synthesize and validate a framework on the digital finance skills necessary for the employees of the banking and finance sector.

3. The INFINITECH Digital Finance Skills Framework

3.1 Overview

The digital transformation of banking and finance hinges not only on the modernization of the technical infrastructure of financial organizations, but also on the enhancement of employees' digital finance skills. As a first step for addressing this skills challenge, leaders need to identify the different sets of digital finance skills required and to understand their relative importance for each competence. Each of these different but interdependent knowledge areas, encapsulates a series of competences for banking and finance professionals. This White Paper proposes a framework composed of different knowledge areas aiming to further inform on the digital finance skills gap. More specifically, the framework includes six different knowledge areas relevant to digital finance skills including Data Management and Data Engineering, Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, Digital Infrastructure and Security, Regulatory and Compliance, Digital Finance Application, and Decentralized Finance as illustrated in Figure 2. For each of the six knowledge areas, below we explain why it is important for the banking and finance sector and shed light on its potential added value with regards to the different related competences.

Figure 2 – Overview of the INFINITECH Digital Finance Skills Framework

3.2 Digital Infrastructure and Security

The wider use of cutting-edge technologies in the field alongside with the wider adoption of financial technologies by the customers increase the complexity of managing and protecting critical digital infrastructures in the banking and finance sector. Professionals need to enhance their skills on managing the security of the institution's cyber-physical infrastructures. This knowledge area includes skills which should be possessed by professionals of the banking and finance sector. It includes the following competences:

- **Cloud Computing:** Cloud computing skills are necessary for the development, deployment, and operation of cloud computing infrastructures, platforms, and cloud enabled services.
- **Edge Computing:** Edge computing skills are necessary for the development, deployment, and operation of edge computing infrastructures, platforms, and cloud enabled services.
- **Distributed Computing:** Distributed computing skills for integrating data and services from multiple distributed computing services.
- **Cybersecurity:** Cybersecurity is a critical element for the safe and reliable deployment and use of infrastructure and systems. Thus, there is a need for cyber security competences, including for example skills relating to security processes and to secure operations of various types of infrastructure and services.
- **Security Risk Assessment:** Capability of designing and implementing security risk assessment procedures for the cyber-physical infrastructures and systems of the banking and finance sector.

3.3 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

While artificial intelligence and machine learning can better facilitate and infuse the analysis of financial data to discover correlations, important insights, make predictions or recommendations, it is necessary for professionals to have a better understanding of the data sources constructs and analytical methods and tools as well as translate it into business value. Thus, this category refers to competences on:

- **Artificial Intelligence:** Artificial Intelligence skills refer to the capacity of the professionals to use AI algorithms to take more informed, data-backed and cost-effective decisions.
- **Machine Learning:** These skills enable the clustering and analysis data using Machine Learning (ML).
- **Natural Language Processing (NLP):** NLP skills to the capability of professionals to extract requested patterns from free data and to interpret the raw data into meaningful insights using NLP tools for data collection, analysis, alerting, and prediction.
- **Robotics Process Automation (RPA):** Refers to the ability to develop and use software aimed at automating finance processes.
- **Bias Management in AI:** Refers to the skills in handling and preventing AI bias in the banking and finance sector by ensuring the right data and algorithms testing and putting together the most adequate practices for data gathering and use and for the creation of AI algorithms.

3.4 Regulations and Compliance

New national and international regulations are applicable to the finance sector to protect the consumers' rights while the institutions increase their use of technology. These include a wide spectrum from codes of conduct and ethics to legal frameworks. To this end, this category encapsulates specific competences on:

- **AI Ethics:** Ensuring that AI tools and algorithms applied in the finance and banking sector are aligned with accountability, transparency, and data bias directions.
- **GDPR:** Refer to skills on ensuring the compliance with GDPR regulations such as clients and other individuals associated with the institution can have adequate control over how their own data are stored, processes or transmitted.

- **PSD2:** Encapsulate skills which can ensure the financial institution's services are aligned with the Payment Services Directive 2 (PSD2) on customers' online transactions.
- **4AML:** Refer to the skills on ensuring the institution follows the Fourth Anti-Money Laundering Directive ("AML IV") on money laundering and terrorist financing.
- **MiFID II:** Skills on facilitating the compliance of financial institutions towards the functionality of financial markets and the protection for investors in alignment with MiFID II.
- **EU Taxonomy:** Refer to the ability of the professionals to ensure the institutions economic activities meet the criteria of the EU Taxonomy on performance.
- **UCITS:** Skills associated with implementing the necessary procedures for the institution to ensure the collective investment in transferable securities are aligned with the UCITS directive.
- **EU Green Bond Financing:** Ensuring that the institution follows the EU-wide standard such that it can encourage market participants to issue and invest in EU green bonds and improve the effectiveness, transparency, comparability & credibility of the market in alignment with the EU Green Bond Financing.

3.5 Data Management and Data Engineering

Financial institutions have access and collect large numbers of data which needs to be cleaned and prepared for further data analysis. Thus, professionals need to be able to develop and manage large volumes of data and to convert raw data into clean and usable data which are available and can be used productively by data scientists or algorithms. This includes competences on:

- **Data integration:** Ability to integrate data from different sources to facilitate a unified view to professionals and customers.
- **Data Strategy:** Refers to the skills on building strategies for leveraging data in order to reach greater efficiencies, resolving challenges and improving customer experience.
- **Data Analysis and Interpretation:** Skills which enables the professionals to adequately analyze data and interpret the data analysis results to take more informed decisions.
- **Data Visualization and Communication:** Abilities associated with using tools in order to derive visuals to communicate the results of data analyses and implications.
- **Statistical and Mathematical Modelling:** Skills on building mathematical models and statistical assumptions to represent financial situations aiming to generate sample data and make predictions.
- **Data Wrangling:** Skills on cleaning errors from data sets and/or restructuring complex datasets aiming to make them more appropriate and relevant to the desired analysis.
- **Data Intuition:** Ability to use data in order to make generalizations or predictions.

3.6 Digital Finance Applications

Financial technologies elevate the efficiency and effectiveness of different banking and finance services from wealth management to know your customer services and chatbots. To this end, professionals need to have knowledge on how to use digital finance applications for completing basic banking and finance services. More specifically, this knowledge area includes competences on:

- **Trading and Stocks:** Skills on using applications which facilitate the buying and selling of stocks.
- **Personal Finance Management (PFM):** Ability to use and assist customers in using the personal finance and mobile banking software available by the institution.

- **Know Your Customer (KYC):** Skills on using applications for conducting an adequate know your customer procedure including establishing customer identity, understanding the nature of customers' activities and qualifying the legitimacy of the source funds etc.
- **Customer Analytics:** Skills associated with using customer analytics tools in order to better understand consumer behavior in the banking and finance sector and streamline products and processes accordingly.
- **Fraud Detection:** Ability to use software and tools which conduct fraud detection tests.
- **Anti-Money Laundering (AML):** Skills on using AML software.
- **ESG Investments:** Ability to use tools designed for better facilitating ESG investments so as to better calculate the investment's financial returns and its overall impact.
- **Credit Underwriting:** Skills on using software and applications for verifying the credibility of customers necessary for approving loans or other products.
- **Credit Risk Assessment:** Skills on using applications for conducting customer credit risk evaluation.
- **Usage Based Insurance:** Skills relevant to using tools and applications for conducting usage-based insurance.
- **Chatbots:** Ability to use the chatbots facilitated by the financial institution.

3.7 Decentralized Finance

With the rise and wider use of digital currencies and relevant by-products, digital finance professionals need to understand blockchain technology and relevant applications. More specifically, this knowledge area includes competences on:

- **Blockchain:** Understanding the functionality and capabilities of blockchain technology for the banking and finance sector.
- **Bitcoin:** Skills on trading and managing cryptocurrency assets including Bitcoin.
- **Ethereum:** Skills on trading and managing cryptocurrency assets including Ethereum.
- **Altcoins:** Skills on trading and managing cryptocurrency assets including Altcoin.
- **Smart Contracts:** Abilities relevant to direct the institution on the relevance and use of smart contracts for the different procedures conducted by financial institutions.
- **Decentralized Consensus:** Skills on participating in distributed network in order to arrive to an agreement on the basis of a shared document or database.
- **Blockchain Payments:** Skills associated with using blockchain to facilitate payments.
- **Blockchain Investments:** Skills associated with using blockchain to facilitate investments.

4. The INFINITECH Skills Survey: Methodology and Key Findings

4.1 Survey Design

The framework guided the design of the digital finance skills survey which aimed at empirically evaluating the extend of the demand in the banking and finance market. This approach led to the identification of digital finance skills which hold the highest relevance in the banking and finance market. The methodology followed includes:

- **Designing the survey in-line with the Digital Finance Skills Framework:** The team drew on the framework to construct the items of the survey. Thus, the survey comprised lists of IoT-related skills which participants were invited to rate using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Very Low) to 5 (Very High). Then the survey was uploaded on Google Forms to facilitate online data collection. This approach assisted the collection of data on the perceived importance of each skill for each participant. Then the final score was calculated based on the total weighted average of the responses.
- **Data collection and sample population:** The target audience of this survey were professionals from the banking and finance and adjacent sectors. The online survey was initially piloted by a number of participants who were part of the target audience and then participants who were part of the sample population were invited to complete the survey online. Overall, 68 respondents participated in the survey. The sample population comprised of 67.6% men and 30.9%. Participants were of all different age cohorts (Figure 3) signaling that a representative sample of different professional levels provided their insights and from a variety of countries (Figure 4). Most of the participants' main area of focus ranged has been Fintech (44.1%), Finance (27.9%), Banking (16.2%) whereas there has been also smaller participation from other areas of focus such as the regulatory and accounting areas.
- **Analysis:** The analysis of the results led to the identification of the most important and least important digital finance skills for the banking and finance sector. Skills included under the same knowledge included in separate knowledge areas could only be indirectly compared.

4.2 Key Findings

The analysis of the data collected show that the Digital Infrastructure and Security knowledge area and especially competences relevant to cyber security and the capability to conduct security risk assessments are of highest importance. Cloud computing has also highlighted as important whereas edge computing and distributed computing have been rated as less important. The results are illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Digital Infrastructure & Security competences

The survey also collected data on the competences associated with the Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning knowledge area. Participants have identified machine learning as the most important competence followed by bias management in AI. As illustrated in Figure 4, natural language processing and robotics process automation are considered as the least important competences of this knowledge area.

Figure 4 – Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning competences

Participants reported on the relevance of competences of the Regulatory and Compliance knowledge area noting that GDPR is the most important competence. They also identified PSD2, MiFID II and 4AML as important. The results regarding all competences included in this knowledge area are reported in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Regulatory & Compliance competences

Regarding the Data Management and Data Engineering knowledge area, the participants noted that capability for Data Analysis and Interpretation is the most important, followed by Data Strategy and Data Visualization and Communication competences. All competences rated under this knowledge area and their importance are included in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Data Management & Data Engineering competences

Competences associated with Digital Finance Application knowledge area are also rated as relatively important. The most important competences are relevant to know-your-customer, anti-money laundering, fraud detection, customer analytics and credit risk assessment applications. Figure 7 illustrates all competences and relevant ratings for each of the competences under this knowledge area.

Figure 7 – Digital Finance applications competences

Competences relevant to Decentralized Finance were also included in the survey. Respondents were invited to rate eight competences under this knowledge area. Blockchain and smart contracts are considered as the most important. Along the same lines, knowledge on decentralized consensus and smart contracts are also important. Figure 8 presents the results associated with this knowledge area in more depth.

Figure 8 – Decentralized Finance related competences

The results of the survey show that all knowledge areas included in the Digital Finance Skills Framework presented in this paper are relevant and important for the digital finance professionals of the future. Security, machine learning, GDPR, data analysis and interpretation, know-your-customer, anti-money laundering, blockchain and smart contracts are some of the most important competences for the banking and finance professionals. The next section further reflects on the findings of this study and the implications for the Digital Finance Skills Framework.

5. Digital Finance Skills Learning Paths

5.1 Using the Digital Finance Skills Framework

The INFINITECH DFSF is a useful tool for Human Resources (HR) professionals and policy makers that develop training programs and policies respectively. Specifically, it can serve as reference model for discovering digital finance skills and their interrelationships. It can be used in the following use cases:

- **Supporting Hiring Processes:** HR professionals can use the framework in order to identify the skills that they must look out for when hiring digital finance roles. The framework can serve as a guide for understanding the combinations of skills that comprise certain skills profiles.
- **Career Development Paths (CDP):** Companies can leverage the framework in order to design CDPs for their employees in digital finance roles. In particular, the framework can enable them to identify the skillsets that will drive the employees' career development pathways. They can also design training programmes and upskilling processes to help the employees in achieving their career development goals.
- **Educational Policies Development:** Banks and financial institutions can leverage the framework as part of their educational policies development. Specifically, the framework can indicate the directions of the education policies, as well as the design of relevant training programmes.
- **Development of Skills Profiles:** In conjunction with the outcomes of the skills survey, the framework can be used to develop skills profiles with the highest possible market relevance. For instance, it is possible to combine popular and complementary skills into skills profiles.

5.2 Skills Profiles and Learning Paths

The clustering of multiple knowledge areas into skills profiles can also drive the specification of training curricula and learning paths that lead to specific digital finance roles. In particular, the DFSF can help professionals to identify the knowledge areas they have to address towards developing their career in-line with the requirements of specific roles. Moreover, it can drive the specification of learning pathways (i.e., collections of courses and other didactic activities) that lead to the acquisition of the desired skills. In this way, the framework can support the formulation of meaningful training programs for academic or professional development i.e., coherent programs with clear market relevance.

The development of such learning paths can be further supported by the training catalogue of the INFINITECH VDIH (Virtualized Digital Innovation Hub)³. This training catalogue comprises tens of training courses and resources, including resources developed by the INFINITECH project, resources available in training platforms like Udemy⁴ and Coursera⁵, as well as resources developed by Universities and Academic organizations. Specifically, it is possible to specify learning paths for entire skills profiles leveraging courses of the catalogue. In this way, INFINITECH can provide pointers to readily available learning resources in support of specific skills profile.

³ <https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/vdih>

⁴ <http://www.udemy.com>

⁵ <http://www.coursera.com>

5.3 Learning Paths Examples

Leveraging the DFSF and the INFINITECH VDIH training catalogue it is possible to specify specific learning paths for various skills profiles. The following tables provide examples of learning paths based on the INFINITECH training catalogue for the following skills profiles:

- **Machine Learning Engineer for Digital Finance**, which is a profile driven by the most popular competences of the AI/ML knowledge area.
- **DeFi Expert**, which is a skills profile directly derived from the respective knowledge area of the INFINITECH framework.
- **Digital Finance Regulations Professional**, which comprises competences of the Regulation and Compliance expert.
- **Cyber Security Expert**, a skills profile with competences associated with the security of the digital and physical infrastructures.
- **Distributed Systems Engineer** comprises competences associated with managing cloud, edge and distributed computing infrastructures of the banking and finance institution.
- **Data Manager and Strategist**, a profile specializing on the competences of analysing, visualizing data and using data to develop strategies for banking and finance institutions.
- **Retail and Digital Banking Expert**, skills associated with performing key banking procedures such as KYC, Credit Underwriting etc.

Digital Finance Skills Profile: ML Engineer for Digital Finance	
Individual Skills of the Profile	
Basic Digital Finance, Basic Fintech, Trading, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Reinforcement Learning, Data Analysis	
INFINITECH Catalogue Courses of the Learning Path	
1.	FinTech – Prepare for the revolution in Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/fintech-prepare-for-the-revolution-in-finance)
2.	Deep Learning and Neural Networks for Financial Engineering (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/deep-learning-and-neural-networks-for-financial-engineering)
3.	Machine Learning and Reinforcement Learning in Finance Specialization (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/machine-learning-and-reinforcement-learning-in-finance-specialization)
4.	Using Machine Learning in Trading and Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/using-machine-learning-in-trading-and-finance)
Other Relevant Courses	
1.	Practical Machine Learning: Real World Projects In Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/practical-machine-learning-real-world-projects-in-finance)
2.	Classical Machine Learning for Financial Engineering (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/classical-machine-learning-for-financial-engineering)

Table 1: Sample Learning Path for the Skills Profile: “ML Engineer for Digital Finance”

Digital Finance Skills Profile: Decentralized Finance Expert	
Individual Skills of the Profile	
Basic Digital Finance, Basic Fintech, Smart Contracts, Blockchain, Cryptoassets	
INFINITECH Catalogue Courses of the Learning Path	
1.	Blockchain: Understanding Its Uses and Implications (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/blockchain-understanding-its-uses-and-implications)
2.	Introduction to Blockchain for Financial Services (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/introduction-to-blockchain-for-financial-services)
3.	Blockchain, Cryptoassets, and Decentralized Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/blockchain-cryptoassets-and-decentralized-finance)
4.	Blockchain In Banking Industry & Enterprise Application (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/blockchain-in-banking-industry-enterprise-application)
Other Relevant Courses	
1.	AI and Blockchain: A Disruptive Integration (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/ai-and-blockchain-a-disruptive-integration)
2.	Supply Chain Finance and Blockchain Technology Specialization (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/supply-chain-finance-and-blockchain-technology-specialization)

Table 2: Sample Learning Path for the Skills Profile: “DeFi Expert”

Digital Finance Skills Profile: Digital Finance Regulations Professional	
Individual Skills of the Profile	
Basic Digital Finance, Basic Fintech, FinTech Ethics, FinReg	
INFINITECH Catalogue Courses of the Learning Path	
1.	FinTech – Prepare for the revolution in Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/fintech-prepare-for-the-revolution-in-finance)
2.	Open Banking, PSD2 and GDPR (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/open-banking-psd2-and-gdpr-fintech)
3.	FinTech Ethics and Risks (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/fintech-ethics-and-risks)
4.	FinTech: Finance Industry Transformation and Regulation Specialization (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/fintech-finance-industry-transformation-and-regulation-specialization)
Other Relevant Courses	
1.	The Professional RegTech Certificate (https://training.fintech.global/courses/professional-regtech-certificate) ⁶
2.	Digital Transformation in Financial Services Specialization (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/digital-transformation-in-financial-services-specialization)

Table 3: Sample Learning Path for the Skills Profile: “Digital Finance Regulations Professional”

⁶ Resource outside the INFINITECH Training Catalogue

Digital Finance Skills Profile: CyberSecurity Expert	
Individual Skills of the Profile	
Basic Digital Finance, Basic Fintech, Cyber Attacks Prevention, Security Risk Assessments	
INFINITECH Catalogue Courses of the Learning Path	
1.	FinTech – Prepare for the revolution in Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/fintech-prepare-for-the-revolution-in-finance)
2.	IT/OT Security Awareness Training (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/it-ot-security-awareness-training)
3.	High-quality training for computer security teams I (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/high-quality-training-for-computer-security-teams-i)
4.	High-quality training for computer security teams II (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/high-quality-training-for-computer-security-teams-ii)
Other Relevant Courses	
1.	Certified Information Security Manager (CISM) (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/certified-information-security-manager-cism)

Table 4: Sample Learning Path for the Skills Profile: “Cybersecurity Expert”

Digital Finance Skills Profile: Distributed Systems Engineer	
Individual Skills of the Profile	
Basic Digital Finance, Basic Fintech, Cloud Computing, Edge Computing Distributed Computing	
INFINITECH Catalogue Courses of the Learning Path	
1.	FinTech – Prepare for the revolution in Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/fintech-prepare-for-the-revolution-in-finance)
2.	Financial Technology and Computing (https://www.usi.ch/en/education/master/financial-technology-and-computing)
3.	Cloud Computing Fundamentals (https://www.udemy.com/course/welcome-to-cloud-computing-world/)
4.	Edge Computing – A Complete Guide on Computing at the Edge (https://www.udemy.com/course/edge-computing-a-complete-guide-on-computing-at-the-edge/?src=sac&kw=edge+com)
Other Relevant Courses	
1.	AI and Blockchain: A Disruptive Integration (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/ai-and-blockchain-a-disruptive-integration)
2.	Supply Chain Finance and Blockchain Technology Specialization (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/supply-chain-finance-and-blockchain-technology-specialization)

Table 5: Sample Learning Path for the Skills Profile: “Distributed Systems Engineer”

Digital Finance Skills Profile: Data Manager and Strategist	
Individual Skills of the Profile	
Basic Digital Finance, Basic Fintech, Data Strategy, Data Analysis, Data Visualization, Data Interpretation	
INFINITECH Catalogue Courses of the Learning Path	
1.	FinTech – Prepare for the revolution in Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/fintech-prepare-for-the-revolution-in-finance)

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Data Strategy Executive Program (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/data-strategy-executive-program) 3. Complete 2-in-1 Python for Business and Finance Bootcamp (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/complete-2-in-1-python-for-business-and-finance-bootcamp)
Other Relevant Courses
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MsC in Data Science & Analytics (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/msc-in-data-science-analytics) 2. The Data Analyst Course: Complete Data Analyst Bootcamp 2022 (https://www.udemy.com/course/the-data-analyst-course-complete-data-analyst-bootcamp/)

Table 6: Sample Learning Path for the Skills Profile: “Data Manager & Strategist”

Digital Finance Skills Profile: Retail and Digital Banking Expert
Individual Skills of the Profile
Basic Digital Finance, Basic Fintech, KYC, Credit Underwriting, Credit Risk Assessment
INFINITECH Catalogue Courses of the Learning Path
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FinTech – Prepare for the revolution in Finance (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/fintech-prepare-for-the-revolution-in-finance) 2. Retail and Digital Banking (https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/training/retail-and-digital-banking-msc) 3. Customer Due Diligence (https://www.udemy.com/course/kyc-cdd-edd/)
Other Relevant Courses
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Complete and Ultimate Guide to Know Your Client (KYC) (https://www.udemy.com/course/complete-kyc/)

Table 7: Sample Learning Path for the Skills Profile: “Retail and Digital Banking Expert”

4. Conclusions

This whitepaper introduced three complementary resources which can help HR professionals, training stakeholders and policy makers in their efforts to define training programs for digital finance roles. These resources include:

1. **The INFINITECH Digital Finance Skills Framework**, which provides a taxonomy of skills for digital finance, including information about their interrelationships. These skills can be directly associated with knowledge areas and competences, as well as with training resources that can foster their development.
2. **A Digital Finance Skills Survey**, which rated the competences of the DFSF based on empirical data collected from professionals in banking, finance, and related fields. The survey provides insights for the relevant importance of the various competence areas and skills, including information about their market relevance. The survey served as a useful tool for identifying and selecting the most important competence areas of digital finance skills profiles and related professionals' roles.
3. **The INFINITECH training catalogue**, which enables professionals to identify courses which correspond to the different knowledge areas of digital finance, including the areas that are included in the DFSF. Based on the catalogue, training stakeholders can define structured learning approaches that encapsulate different sets of available learning resources.

In the scope of the present whitepaper, the DFSF has been introduced, along with the main findings of the skills survey. Moreover, the INFINITECH training catalogue has been used to specify concrete learning paths for popular skills profiles. The above-listed resources are accessible through the INFINITECH marketplace and VDIH. They are offered for free and with unlimited access to the INFINITECH community.

5. Complementary Resources & More Information

Stay up to date about the INFINITECH solutions, assets and services through:

- Visiting the INFINITECH project web site: <https://www.infinitech-h2020.eu/>
- Subscribing to the INFINITECH YouTube Channel:
<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCIVeOyQyljdCpL51GSPa7Zg>
- Subscribe to the INFINITECH Newsletter at: <https://www.infinitech-h2020.eu/contact-us>
- Registering to INFINITECH Marketplace: <https://marketplace.infinitech-h2020.eu/>
- Contacting us using the contact form at: <https://www.infinitech-h2020.eu/contact-us>

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